

The Enigmatic Granuloma Annulare - A Review of Its Clinical, Etiopathological and Therapeutic Options

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Abstract:

Granuloma annulare, persistent inflaming collagenolytic disorder mainly affecting cutaneous and subcutaneous tissue found in children and adults. Granuloma annulare is a non-infectious granulomatous disorder having etiological provokers. The common variants are localized, generalized, perforating and subcutaneous. In few studies done recently new insights furnished into the epidemiology and causes of GA, along with potential treatment options, although randomized controlled trials remain limited. This review highlights the latest developments in GA epidemiology, pathogenesis, and available therapies, with the aim of encouraging further research and evidence-based treatment recommendations for GA.

Keywords: Granuloma annulare, Collagenolytic disorder, Epidemiology, Pathogenesis.

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Introduction

The term “ringed eruption of fingers” was first described in a girl of 11 years by Calcott fox in the year 1895. [1] The entity ‘granuloma annulare’ description given by Radcliffe-Crocker in 1902. [2] Granuloma annulare (GA) considered as non-infectious skin disease which appear as granulomatous inflammation, which can occur in both adults and children. While the exact cause of GA remains unclear, factors such as infections, medications, trauma, insect bites, vaccinations, have been noted as potential triggers. [3-5]

GA is considered a self-resolving, benign state which is usually asymptomatic, some cases may involve mild itching. GA can appear in all aspects of body but is usually found to appear on the sides or dorsal aspects of the hands and feet. The condition presented as isolated, erythematous, ring shaped papules and plaques, mainly appearing on the peripheral areas. [6,7] It is crucial to segregate GA from more round lesions, such as erythema annulare centrifugum, tinea cruris, sarcoidosis, pityriasis rosea, urticarial, Hansen's disease, and subacute cutaneous lupus erythematosus. [8-10] In

adults, GA has been linked to diabetes, hyperlipidaemia, and malignancies. Certain cancers such as lymphoma and prostate cancer has also been found to be linked to the conditions. [11-13] Detection of the disease is based on both clinical and histopathological findings. Histopathological examination typically reveals collagen breakdown, mucin accumulation, and a lymphohistiocytic infiltrate. [14,15] Umbet et al., conducted a study where the most encountered histological variant of GA is presence of histiocytes between collagen bundles, and few necrobiosis (72%), collagenolytic granulomas (25%) and epithelioid nodules (3%). The histiocytes with membrane activity having huge mitochondria, abundant lysosomes, and fully-formed rough endoplasmic reticulum were electron microscopic findings. [16]

In this review, we encapsulated latest findings about the epidemiology, causes, and development of GA, along with an overview of the new treatment choices. We recognize the absence of randomized trials as a limitation, so we have done thorough evaluation of the existing observational

studies to avoid potential bias additionally to assess the strength of the proof supporting the treatments discussed.

Materials and Methods

We carried a literature exploration on PubMed. Using the search term “GRANULOMA ANNULARE” to obtain outcome. We included studies that reported on the effectiveness or ineffectiveness of specific treatments, including case studies and case series, but excluded commentaries, editorials.

Epidemiology

A research conducted by Barbieri et al., involving cases whose newly diagnosed GA and with existing GA, provides insight into the epidemiology of the condition in U.S. according to the researchers, the incidence of GA to be 0.04% which is prevalent more in the fifth decade with female preponderance. The study also comments on frequently prescribed treatments for GA. The local and intralesional corticosteroids are the preferred therapies. With 41.5% of cases receiving a prescription for local corticosteroids and 9.4% obtaining intralesional corticosteroid injections in a period of six months of diagnosis. The hydroxychloroquine (HCQ) and tetracycline and were also used as foremost therapy. Although phototherapy is considered the highly effective.

Clinical and Histological Presentation and Differential Diagnosis

A. Clinical Presentation

Granuloma annulare is a disorder of cutaneous and subcutaneous tissue which appear with granulomatous papules, nodules, annular plaques, with aggregation of altered collagen which is circled by histiocytes and lymphocytes. The main variants of GA are localised, generalized (disseminated), subcutaneous, perforating and rarer variants is patch-type. The clinical features of GA mainly depends on the variant occurring in the patient. Coexistence of more than one clinical variant is seen. [18]

Description of each variant are as follows:

Localized GA –

The frequent usual variant of GA (75-80%). The term ‘annulare’ of GA relate to the lesion’s configuration, found in localized forms of GA, presents as single, pale-coloured to red-coloured circinate papules and plaques. [14] On pulling the skin the raised lesions appear as promptly. The papules has intact surface with no scaling. Common sites are dorsum of hands, knuckles, fingers, and feet.

Generalized (disseminated) GA-

Seen in 10-15% of cases. [19,20] Predominantly in adults with female dominance. It is the commonest form prevalent in HIV patients and presents with pruritus. [19]. Presents with massive fashion, with generalized (i.e. disseminated) GA which is described as at least 10 round plaques.

Subcutaneous GA-

Subcutaneous GA is a type of GA and found among children. It usually appear as a firm, subcutaneous lesion on the bottom limbs. [21]

Patch GA

Patch type GA, a rarer type and appear as violaceous to red patches that usually found in both the near extremities. [22]

Perforating GA

Perforating GA is identified as umbilicated papules or pustules with crusting that can be either isolated [23] or widespread. [24]

Although rare, GA has also been observed on peripheral surfaces, including the palms and soles of the feet.

B. Histological Features

The histological finding of granuloma annulare (GA) is seen as a focus of necrobiosis encircled by palisading histiocytes. Another key feature of GA is the deposition of mucin. Additionally, multinucleated giant cells are frequently observed, along with the presence of eosinophils, lymphocytes, and neutrophils infiltrating the dermis. Umbet et al., conducted a study where the frequent histological variant of GA is presence of histiocytes between collagen bundles, with few necrobiosis (72%), palisading granulomas (25%) and epithelioid nodules (3%) [16]

C. Differential Diagnosis

Granuloma annulare can mimic more granulomatous skin conditions like necrobiosis lipoidica and sarcoidosis but presence of mucin is an important hallmark which help in diagnosis of GA. [14] Recently GA has been reported along with many diseases like tinea cruris [28], psoriasis [29], papulonecrotic tuberculid [30], dermatofibroma [31], dermatomyositis [32], borreliasis [33], tuberculoid leprosy [34], Kaposi sarcoma [35].

Etiopathogenesis and Associated Comorbidities-Update

In the study conducted in last years has indicated that apart from cell types T-helper 2 and T- helper 1, the Janus Kinase Transducer Transcription Activator (Janus kinase-signal transducer and activator of transcription) pathway contributes to etiopathogenesis of GA.

In a review conducted by Wang et al., increase of mRNA of important modulators were described in the JAK-STAT pathway, such as , oncostatin M, IL-15, IL-12- , oncostatin M,. Upregulation polarization of “M1” macrophage and polarization of “M2” macrophase were described by Wang et al. [36]

Chronic Comorbidities

GA is linked to diabetes, hyperlipidaemia, and malignancies. GA has been found to be instigated by Diabetes and Hyperlipidaemia by a common pathway of T-cell dysregulation. GA is also driver by autoimmunity which is evident in association of GA and autoimmune diseases (RA and SLE). [37] Hypothyroidism and ischaemic heart disease has been found to be associated to GA. [38]

In a study conducted by Barbieri, cases having GA showed a good quantity of higher possibility of developing lymphoma, leukaemia and any hematologic cancer. Age-based analyses showed consistent findings in patients aged 51-70 and those over 70; however, there was no statistically significant increase in the risk of hematologic cancers in those under 50.

Various infections associated with GA and also act as a trigger are-

- **Bacterial** - Borrelia and Chlamydiales [40]
- **Viral Infections** –Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV), varicella zoster virus (VZV) [42,43], Epstein-Barr virus [41] , and Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-Cov-2) [44,45] .

The study conducted by Shah et al. causes of cutaneous drug eruptions are amlodipine, levetiracetam, paroxetine, pegylated IFN- α , secukinumab, tocilizumab, topiramate, and vemurafenib; immune checkpoint inhibitors; intranasal calcitonin; gold; botulinum toxin; dabrafenib; desensitization injections; vaccines (hepatitis B and anti-tetanus vaccination). [46] The specific origin of drug-induced granuloma annulare (GA) is unknown, and it is particularly mysterious when GA is brought on by anti-TNF α drugs and apremilast since both of these medications have been shown to be effective in treating GA.

Treatment Options:

Topical and intralesional corticosteroids are regarded as primary treatments for GA and leads to some or complete response in certain cases. However, some patient of GA do not respond to corticosteroid therapy. [17,47]

In latest case series involving cases with patch-type GA revealed that somewhat inferior feedback to corticosteroids, of only 5 out of 20 patient’s therapy with topical corticosteroids exhibited response. [22] Despite the moderate effectiveness,

corticosteroids continue to be a reasonable first-line treatment option due to their relative safety and affordability. However, it is not uncommon for GA to be resistant to corticosteroids, often requiring the use of second-line therapies.

Antimicrobials that are found to be effective in GA are- Doxycycline [48], Minocycline, Ofloxacin, Rifampicin [49], and Dapsone [50]. Since Dapsone has risk of immunosuppression, it should be used with caution.

Antimalarial drug such as hydroxychloroquine is effective, well-tolerated in GA as well as cheap drug. Xu et al. accounted a child achieving full abeyance of disseminated GA with 25mg everyday dose of HCQ for a period six month. [51] Megna et al. documented a case of complete resolution of disseminated GA in cases following an 8-week treatment with 200 mg of HCQ two times daily. [52]

Apremilast, phosphodiesterase-4 inhibitor has been found to work as a double- edge sword in GA. There has also been a contradictory case of GA developing with initiating apremilast as treatment option for psoriasis. 53Bishnoi et al. presented a clinical series involving four GA cases treated with apremilast, where most patients showed a reduce in lesion count and one felt reduced redness and itching. Out of four cases, improvement was observed within 6 to 8 weeks of starting apremilast treatment. [54]

In 2019, Chen et al. conducted an analysis on the use with biologic therapies for chronic GA. Their pooled analysis highlighted the potential of TNF- α inhibitors, with fourteen out of sixteen patients managed with adalimumab showing improvement, along with 1/5 patients treated with etanercept, and all 3/5 patients receiving Infliximab. Additionally, a case getting treatment with a combination of Infliximab and Adalimumab also experiencing positive response. [55]

Methotrexate also used as second line therapy for GA being an immunomodulatory, cost effective drug with continuous monitoring of adverse events (myelosuppression).

A derivative of methylxanthine, Pentoxifylline which has anti-inflammatory effects, potential treatment option for managing GA in certain patients. [56] Like HCQ, pentoxifylline is an affordable and generally proper-tolerated small molecule, warranting more investigation in randomized controlled trials.

The Phototherapy has been found to be efficient in treatment of GA and be considered as second line therapy keeping in mind the safety side and few efficacy. But phototherapy is not cost effective and its use has been reduced in recent years. [57,58]. The modalities of phototherapy used are PDT

(photodynamic therapy) [47], Ultraviolet A1(UVA1), psoralen plus UVA(PUVA) Narrowband UVB (NB-UVB). [59]

The inhibitor of JAK, Tofacitinib, is rapidly becoming popular in dermatology for its broad range of uses. It has demonstrated off-label effectiveness in treating various inflammatory conditions, including psoriasis, alopecia areata, vitiligo and atopic dermatitis. [60] Two cases have been reported where patients experienced almost complete subsidence of their GA after using topical tofacitinib, indicating that the topical form of the drug may also be effective. However, it is important to note that JAK-STAT inhibitors are costly making them a potential option only as a last-resort treatment. [61,62]. Other treatment options available are- Sulphasalazine, [63] Potassium Iodide (KI), [64] Oral Isotretinoin and Cyclosporin. [49]

Conclusion

In recent years, new research on GA has provided a proper review of its epidemiology, with latest studies shedding light on its pathogenesis, identifying dysregulation in the Th1, JAK-STAT, and possibly Th2 pathways in GA-affected skin. The most discussed association of diabetes mellitus (DM) and GA now appears that its confirmed, but the link of GA and malignancy stays disputed. Recent viral and bacterial triggers has been considered, though it is unlikely each independently cause GA. Additionally, recent reports have documented drug-induced GA, though the mechanism behind these reactions is unclear, especially given that some drugs both trigger and treat GA.

Regarding treatment, various case reports, series, and observational studies suggest promising responses to certain therapies, though the findings are still limited in scope. Huge retrospective studies contribute effectiveness of topical and intralesional corticosteroids for few, not all cases. With corticosteroid-resistant GA, alternative treatments may be required. The Phototherapy is considered the frequent extensively reviewed option, but latest updates highlight that every patient didn't respond, and monetary and logistical problems may limit access. More affordable oral medications like Dapsone, HCQ, pentoxifylline, and Sulphasalazine and methotrexate, have shown few responses in huge retrospective reviews and are found used as second-line treatments. Immunomodulators which are focussed, including apremilast and tofacitinib, as well as biologic therapies like Dupilumab and TNF- α inhibitors, can be used as treatment option for GA, though proof is justified to verification of case reports and small case series. Addressing frequent adverse diseases like diabetes and hyperlipidemia are found to play a supportive role

in treatment. Based on our review, we suggest a treatment approach of managing GA, starting as topical and intralesional corticosteroids as foremost step. If corticosteroids prove ineffective, treatment can be escalated to the next level, which includes Dapsone, pentoxifylline, and Sulphasalazine, HCQ, methotrexate. For cases that remain resistant to these treatments, phototherapy, and targeted immunomodulators like tofacitinib and apremilast, or biologic therapies (dupilumab, etanercept, adalimumab, and infliximab) are taken account. Considering important to note that GA, particularly the localized form, is often self-limiting and may resolve on its own. For cases that are not related with the cosmetic look of the lesions, reassurance about its benign nature of GA may be sufficient without further treatment.

References

1. Colcott-Fox T. Ringed eruptions of the fingers. *Br J Dermatol.* 1895; 7:91–5.
2. Little EG. Granuloma Annulare. *Br J Dermatol.* 1908; 20:317–35.
3. Takayama K, Satoh T, Yokozeki H. Papular granuloma annulare with subcutaneous granulomatous reaction induced by a bee sting. *Acta Derm Venereol.* 2008; 88(5):519–520. DOI: 10.2340/00015555-0487. PMID: 18779899.
4. Emre S, Unal E, Celik B, Sungu N. The case of granuloma annulare associated with SARS-CoV-2 infection. *Dermatol Ther.* 2022; 35(5):e15369. DOI: 10.1111/dth.15369. PMID: 35142417. PMCID: PMC9111399.
5. Suzuki T, Shimauchi T, Moriki M, Tokura Y. Subcutaneous granuloma annulare following influenza vaccination in a patient with diabetes mellitus. *Dermatologica Sinica.* 2014; 32(1):55–57. DOI: 10.1016/j.dsi.2013.03.004.
6. Joshi TP, Duvic M. Granuloma annulare: an updated review of epidemiology, pathogenesis, and treatment options. *Am J Clin Dermatol.* 2022; 23(1):37–50. PMID: 34495491; PMCID: PMC8423598. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40257-021-00636-1>
7. Piette EW, Rosenbach M. Granuloma annulare: clinical and histologic variants, epidemiology, and genetics. *J Am Acad Dermatol.* 2016; 75(3):457–65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaad.2015.03.05>.
8. Hsu S, Le EH, Khoshevis MR. Differential diagnosis of annular lesions. *Am Fam Physician.* 2001; 64(2):289–96. PMID: 11476274.
9. Shah KK, Pritt BS, Alexander MP. Histopathologic review of granulomatous inflammation. *J Clin Tuberc Other Mycobact Dis.* 2017; 7:1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jctube.2017.02.001>.
10. Orleans RA, Magro CM, Varghese GI. A case of granuloma annulare mimicking tinea cruris.

- Dermatol Online J. 2018; 24(8). <https://doi.org/x10.5070/D3248041160>.
11. Gupta D, Hess B, Bachegowda L. Granuloma annulare. *Sci World J.* 2010; 10:384–6. <https://doi.org/10.1100/tsw.2010.51>
 12. Cyr PR. Diagnosis and management of granuloma annulare. *Am Fam Physician.* 2006; 74:1729–34. PMID: 17137003.
 13. Toro JR, Chu P, Yen T-SB, LeBoit PE. Granuloma annulare and human immunodeficiency virus infection. *Arch Dermatol.* 1999; 135(11):1341–6. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archderm.135.11.1341>
 14. Thornsberry LA, English JC. Etiology, diagnosis, and therapeutic management of granuloma annulare: an update. *Am J Clin Dermatol.* 2013; 14(4):279–90. PMID: 23696233. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40257-013-0029-5>.
 15. Dabski K, Winkelmann R. Generalized granuloma annulare: histopathology and immunopathology: systematic review of 100 cases and comparison with localized granuloma annulare. *J Am Acad Dermatol.* 1989; 20(1):28–39. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0190-9622\(89\)70004-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0190-9622(89)70004-9)
 16. Umbert P, Winkelmann R. Histologic, ultrastructural, and histochemical studies of granuloma annulare. *Arch Dermatol.* 1977; 113(12):1681–6. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archderm.1977.01640120049007>.
 17. Barbieri JS, Rodriguez O, Rosenbach M, Margolis D. Incidence and prevalence of granuloma annulare in the United States. *JAMA Dermatol.* 2021;157:824–30
 18. Christopher E. M. Griffiths, Jonathan Barker, Tanya O. Bleaker, Walayat Hussain, Rosalind C. Simpson. *Rook's Textbook of Dermatology.* Wiley-Blackwell:Oxford, 2024.
 19. Dabski K, Winkelmann RK. Generalized granuloma annulare: clinical and laboratory findings in 100 patients. *J Am Acad Dermatol* 1989; 20:39–47.
 20. Muhlbauer JE. Granuloma annulare. *J Am Acad Dermatol* 1980; 3:217–30.
 21. Endo Y, Sekiguchi A, Motegi S, Ishikawa O. Subcutaneous granuloma annulare on the heel: a case report and review of the Japanese published work. *J Dermatol.* 2020; 47:677–9.
 22. Khanna U, North JP. Patch-type granuloma annulare: an institution-based study of 23 cases. *J Cutan Pathol.* 2020; 47:785–93.
 23. Pap N, Bradamante M, Ljubojević HS. Localized perforating granuloma annulare. *Acta Dermatovenerol Croat.* 2019; 27:33–6. 15.
 24. Salzmann M, Rendon A, Toberer F, Hassel JC. Generalized perforating granuloma annulare: a case report. *J Dtsch DermatolGes.* 2021; 19:585–7.
 25. Muse M, Prohaska J, Shah M, White W, Appel J. Granuloma annulare on the palms. *Dermatol Online J.* 2021; 27:13030/qt0m50398n.
 26. Rai T. Papular granuloma annulare of palms and soles. *Indian Dermatol Online J.* 2017; 8:511–3.
 27. Chatterjee D, Kaur M, Punia RPS, Bhalla M, Handa U. Evaluating the unusual histological aspects of granuloma annulare: a study of 30 cases. *Indian Dermatol Online J.* 2018; 9:409–13.
 28. Orleans RA, Magro CM, Varghese GI. A case of granuloma annulare mimicking tinea cruris. *Dermatol Online J.*2018; 24:13030/qt3kz6h4kj.
 29. Witkoff BM, Ivanov NN, Trotter SC. Perforating granuloma annulare appearing as a psoriasisiform lesion. *Case Rep Dermatol.*2019; 11:233–8.
 30. Chae MH, Shin JY, Lee JY, Yoon TY. Perforating granuloma annulare mimicking papulonecrotic tuberculid. *Ann Dermatol.*2018; 30:716–20.
 31. Akay BN, Atak MF, Kirmizi A, Farabi B. Granulomaannulare mimicking eruptive dermatofibroma in an HIV-positive male: a challenge with distinct dermatoscopic findings. *Dermatol Ther.*2020; 33:e13375.
 32. Maoz K, Greenberger S, Maly A, Merims S, Tirosh I, Barzilai A, et al. Subcutaneous granuloma annulare mimicking dermato-myositis. *Pediatric Dermatol.* 2020; 37:687–9.
 33. Saggini A, Cerroni L. Cutaneous borreliosis: an insidious mimicker of patch-type granuloma annulare. *J Cutan Pathol.*2020; 47:876–8.
 34. Zhu TH, Kamangar F, Silverstein M, Fung MA. Borderline tuberculoid leprosy masquerading as granuloma annulare: a clinical and histological pitfall. *Am J Dermatopathol.* 2017; 39:296–9.
 35. Aghazadeh N, Bridges AG, Camilleri MJ, Peters MS, Comfere NI. Kaposi sarcoma misdiagnosed as granuloma annulare: a case of mistaken identity. *J Cutan Pathol.* 2021; 48:318–21.
 36. Wang A, Rahman N-T, McGeary MK, Murphy M, McHenry A, Peterson D, et al. Treatment of granuloma annulare and suppression of proinflammatory cytokine activity with tofacitinib. *J Allergy Clin Immunol.* 2021; 147:1795–809.
 37. Barbieri JS, Rosenbach M, Rodriguez O, Margolis DJ. Association of granuloma annulare with Type 2 Diabetes, hyperlipidaemia, autoimmune disorders, and hematologic malignant neoplasms. *JAMA Dermatol.* 2021; 157:817–23.
 38. Leasure AC, Damsky W, Cohen JM. Comorbidities associated with granuloma annulare: a case-control study in the All of Us research program. *J Am Acad Dermatol.* 2021.

- <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaad.2021.07.033> (Epub 29 Jul 2021).
39. Barbieri JS, Rosenbach M, Rodriguez O, Margolis DJ. Association of granuloma annulare with Type 2 Diabetes, hyperlipidemia, autoimmune disorders, and hematologic malignant neoplasms. *JAMA Dermatol.* 2021; 157:817–23.
 40. Tolkki L, Hokynar K, Meri S, Panelius J, Puolakainen M, Ranki A. Granuloma Annulare and Morphea: Correlation with Borrelia burgdorferi Infections and Chlamydia-related Bacteria. *Acta Derm Venereol.* 2018; 98:355–60.
 41. Guglielmo A, Viridi A, Misciali C, Gabrielli L, Veronesi G, Corsini I, et al. Generalized granuloma annulare-like eruption secondary to acute Epstein-Barr virus infection. *Int J Dermatol.* 2021; 60:e110–2.
 42. Mann E, Maruthi R, Friedland MH, Chung HJ, McGee JS. Case of post-herpetic, isotopic granuloma annulare (GA), followed by generalized GA. *J Dermatol.* 2019; 46:e476–7.
 43. Al Ali A, Alkhodair R, Thuraisingam T, Gerstein W, Watters K. Multiple granuloma annulare lesions presenting simultaneously with herpes zoster infection: Wolf's isotopic response. *JAAD Case Rep.* 2018; 4:631–2.
 44. García-Gil MF, Monte Serrano J, García García M, Matovelle Ochoa C, Ara-Martín M. Granuloma annulare triggered by SARS-CoV-2 infection. The first reported case. *J Dermatol.* 2021; 48:e1–2.
 45. Monte-Serrano J, García-Gil MF, García-García M, Casas-Flecha I, Matovelle-Ochoa C, Ara-Martín M. Granuloma annulare triggered by SARS-CoV-2 infection: immunohistochemical staining. *Dermatol Ther.* 2021; 34:e14897.
 46. Shah N, Shah M, Drucker AM, Shear NH, Ziv M, Dodiuk-Gad RP. Granulomatous cutaneous drug eruptions: a systematic review. *Am J Clin Dermatol.* 2021; 22:39–53.
 47. Wang J, Khachemoune A. Granuloma annulare: a focused review of therapeutic options. *Am J Clin Dermatol.* 2018; 19:333–44.
 48. Eid E, Zein-El-Dine S, Kurban M, Abbas O. Generalized granuloma annulare associated with interstitial lung disease: Good response to doxycycline. *Dermatol Ther.* 2021; 34:e14864.
 49. Visconti MJ, Ashack KA, Ashack RJ. Granuloma annulare: strengthening potential associations and pentoxifylline as a therapeutic option. *J Dermatol Treat.* 2021; 32:381–2.
 50. Rubin CB, Rosenbach M. Granuloma annulare: a retrospective series of 133 patients. *Cutis.* 2019; 103:102–6.
 51. Xu Q, Gu Y, Li Y, Ling B, Yu H, Yao Z. Concurrence of generalized perforating and subcutaneous granuloma annulare in a 4-year-old boy with latent tuberculosis infection successfully treated with low-dose hydroxychloroquine. *J Dermatol.* 2020; 47:e71–2.
 52. Megna M, Sidikov A, Ruggiero A, Fabbrocini G, Zaslavsky D, Nasyrov R, et al. A case of generalized granuloma annulare successfully treated by hydroxychloroquine. *Dermatol Ther.* 2020; 33:e13894.
 53. Fässler M, Schlapbach C. Granuloma annulare arising under systemic psoriasis therapy successfully treated with adalimumab. *JAAD Case Rep.* 2020; 6:832–4.
 54. Bishnoi A, Raj D, Vinay K, Dogra S. Refractory Generalized Granuloma Annulare Treated With Oral Apremilast. *JAMA dermatology (Chicago, IL).* United States: American Medical Association; 2019; 155:1318.
 55. Chen A, Truong AK, Worswick S. The role of biologics in the treatment of chronic granuloma annulare. *Int J Dermatol.* 2019; 58:622–6.
 56. Hassan I, Dorjay K, Anwar P. Pentoxifylline and its applications in dermatology. *Indian*
 57. Aubin F, Chaignot C, Gallais-Serezal I. Société Française de Photodermatologie. Decline in the use of phototherapy in France from 2010 to 2019. *Br J Dermatol.* 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjd.20384> (Epub 9 Apr 2021).
 58. Eadie E, Gallacher M, Gorczynski A, Smith L, Dawe RS. Photonet, the Managed Clinical Network for Ultraviolet (UV) Phototherapy in Scotland. Response to Decline in use of phototherapy in France from 2010 to 2019. *Br J Dermatol.* 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjd.20586> (Epub 17 Jun 2021).
 59. Aichelburg MC, Pinkowicz A, Schuster C, Volc-Platzer B, Tanew A. Patch granuloma annulare: clinicopathological characteristics and response to phototherapy. *Br J Dermatol.* 2019; 181:198–9.
 60. Maloney NJ, Zhao J, Tegtmeier K, Lee EY, Cheng K. Off-label studies on apremilast in dermatology: a review. *J Dermatol Treat.* 2020; 31:131–40.
 61. Durgin JS, Shields BE, Rosenbach M. Generalized granuloma annulare: a widespread response to limited application of compounded 2% topical tofacitinib. *JAAD Case Rep.* 2020; 6:1113–5.
 62. Damsky W, King BA. Treatment of granuloma annulare with tofacitinib 2% ointment. *JAAD Case Rep.* 2020; 6:69–71.
 63. Yang YW, Lehrer MD, Mangold AR, Yiannias JA, Nelson SA, Pittelkow MR. Treatment of granuloma annulare and related granulomatous diseases with sulphasalazine: a series of 16 cases. *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol.* 2021; 35:211–5.
 64. Anzengruber F, Mergenthaler C, Murer C, Dummer R. Potassium Iodide for cutaneous inflammatory disorders: a monocentric. Ret-

rospective Study. *Dermatology*. 2019; 235:13

7-43.